

GETAWAY

weekend hops

Fun and Funky

Denver boasts an array of treats |
By **WILMA ANN ANDERSON**

When you say Denver to me, I think of the performer John Denver—who actually took his stage name from this capital city of Colorado. Then I think cowboys, wide-open spaces and mountains. Well, there's more to Denver than ghosts of tumbleweed-dodging cattle wranglers. Denver is one of the country's fastest-growing cities, not to mention a bumpin' Midwest hotspot. Don't believe me? See for yourself.

After being greeted by aerial views of the Rockies, set your bags downtown at a funky inn like The Curtis Hotel. Color is what the Curtis shouts. There's nothing subdued here, yet it's not overwhelming. Nostalgic treats and trinkets are sold right next to the reservation desk. When was the last time you had penny candy? Every floor of the Curtis has a different theme. I happened to stay on the big-hair floor, and woke up to ample framed art depicting afros and hairsprayed bouffants. You might land on the monster floor or car floor, and relive a time when life was more carefree. And to boot, turn down service includes some fun throwback trivia.

Grab a bite to eat at the Curtis diner-style restaurant or start your Denver experience doing a little sightseeing on the way to a local Chipotle. The restaurant chain was started in Denver and is on a long list of "firsts" that Denver boasts. Not up for Mexican style? Well, try a little

installation in front of Denver Art Museum

down-home flavor at Tom's Home Cookin' restaurant featuring southern classics like peach cobbler, located in Denver's historic Five Points neighborhood. Melt the cobbler away by taking in some history in Five Points—the area just northeast of downtown where Welton, Washington and 27th Streets meet East 26th Avenue. Five Points was once called the "Harlem of the West" because it thrived as the cultural Mecca in Denver. The Rossonian Hotel, now being restored as a live music venue, was once the lodging of choice for greats such as Ella Fitzgerald, Duke Ellington and Charlie Parker, who played downtown spots but weren't allowed to stay downtown due to racist restrictions.

Up for some more cultural attractions? Denver's got plenty. In fact, Denver's an esthetically pleasing city as well; the Denver metro area has a self-imposed 10th of a cent sales tax that, in part, funds public art. Civic Center Park, one of 200 parks within the city (the largest city park system in the country), neighbors the Colorado State Capitol building. The dome of this building is covered with 24k gold; inside you can stand on the step that is exactly a mile above sea level and view the decorative touches of the world's only supply of Colorado onyx. The Golden Triangle museum district boasts the Colorado History Museum, the Denver Art Museum, the Denver Library and the home of Titanic heroine, the "Unsinkable" Molly Brown.

The Black America West Museum tells the story of one-third of the cowboys on the great cattle drives of the 19th century who were African American. A visit to The Blair-Caldwell African American Research Library will reveal more than 150 archival collections that came from African-American gold miners, cowboys, homesteaders, suffragettes, politicians, physicians, artists and musicians, even John Mosley, Tuskegee airman of World War II. Tours and programming for adults and families are avail-

Above: Downtown Denver; below: Welton Street sign

able year-round. A tour of Grace Stiles' home (Stiles African American Heritage Center, Inc.) for a look-see at antiques and original historical documents will round out your museum-hopping experience.

Who would have thought that Denver was an important stop along vaudeville routes? In fact, a theater was the first building in town. A saloon was a quick follow-up! Denver's micro-breweries and pubs offer 80 beers that cannot be found anywhere else in the world. Coors Brewing Company offers free tours and samples to visitors 21 and older.

Denver also boasts a lot of originality. Denver has one of three mints in the U.S. and the majority of state quarters are minted here; the cheeseburger was invented here and the snap button Western shirt popular among rock-stars (www.rockmount.com) started here. There's even an amusement park smack dab in the middle of downtown (elitchgardens.com). Denver is big for bikers and skiers (black ski club: www.slippers-n-sliders.org), and adventure seekers (www.BeckwourthMountainclub.org, an African-American club). This city claims big diversity, including an African-American population of 10 percent and Hispanic population of 33 percent.

Denver has good eats, too. I'm usually not that interested in viewing the process of my food being made. I don't need to see my fish caught and scaled or my corn harvested and husked. But, I had the opportunity to see how the chefs at Riojas do it with their chef-side dining experience. At this funky yet classy spot in Denver's block-long Larimer Square, the patrons are abuzz and the chefs are afire. Chef Jen actually made me fall in love with my nemesis—artichoke hearts!

Did I mention that Denver has over 300 days of sunshine? Enough said.

